

Legal Accountability for Commercial Contracts in Jordan Legislation

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1. Abstract

A contract is traditionally defined as an agreement between two or more parties that creates obligations which are legally enforceable. This definition is comprised of three main elements. Firstly, contracts are voluntary. They arise from the choice of the parties to enter into an agreement, as opposed to being imposed upon them. This is the principle of consensuality; a basic axiom of contract law which varies considerably in its application among different legal systems. Second, contracts create obligations. This serves to distinguish contracts from other consensual agreements which may create moral or social, but not legal obligations. The law of obligations is a major area of the law in most legal systems, and in some it is the dominant feature of private law. Thirdly, contracts are legally enforceable. This is also a basic presumption of modern contract law, and while it may sometimes be presumed in Jordan, there are other times when the ability to enforce the agreement is a major concern of the parties, and even the central reason for entering into the agreement. Enforcement may also be a major issue in terms of a party's ability to choose not to fulfill an obligation, or to request termination of the contract.

This essay will discuss the concept of legal accountability in respect to commercial contracts. The specific focus will be on contracts made in Jordan. The essay will begin with an overview of the general concepts of contract law,¹ identifying the distinctiveness of Jordanian contracts within a broader framework of civil law. This discussion will be structured around the workings and logic of contract law in general, with particular attention on how this operates within civil law jurisdiction.

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1.1. Overview of commercial contracts in Jordan

Jordanian contracts law is closely affiliated with the French legal system, and it is important to take into consideration the opinions of legal scholars and court rulings when interpreting and applying the law. The different interpretations and rulings by courts have caused some uncertainty in the law and have given rise to conflicting

judgments. Due to a lack of clear and consistent precedents, there are frequent disputes regarding the consistency of court rulings with the law. This has led to criticism that contractual rights and obligations are not always certain and enforcement is not always achievable. Uncertainty of the law and lack of clear precedents may affect contractual accountability, and it shall be seen how this may be resolved or improved in the future.

Commercial transactions are an ancient and integral part of Jordan's economy, and the law of contracts is well established. As outlined in the Jordanian Civil Code (Articles 198-374), a contract is an agreement that creates rights and obligations that are enforceable in law. Arabic terminology divides contracts into two main categories: Aqd, a contract that requires certain formalities or conditions to be satisfied for the contract to be valid, and Iqala, meaning a contract that is executed immediately upon agreement between the parties. Both types of contracts are binding between the parties, as long as the contract is legal.

1.2. Importance of legal accountability in commercial contracts

The importance of legal accountability in the commercial contract can be better realized within the context of the role of the written contract itself. The primary objective of putting a transaction into writing is to record the terms and understanding of the parties. This is important because memories fade and recollection of oral agreements can differ. Another reason that written contracts are important is because they act to protect reasonable expectations. This is because when two parties agree to a contract, there are certain benefits that each side is hoping to gain from the agreement. These benefits are likely to be speculative in the sense that they may not eventuate until the completion of the contract. By recording the contract in writing, the parties are able to reduce speculation and protect their reasonable expectations. The identification and enforcement of legal rights and obligations in commercial contracts depend on whether the contract is sufficiently certain. This must be judged on an objective basis, self-evident meaning verifiable from the contract itself. Terms which are implied must also be sufficiently precise. This requirement is to enable the adjudicators to ascertain the content of the term and the intention of the parties. One way that contracts enforce legal rights and obligations is through performance. Non-performance can arise if there are breaches or failures to perform. This can raise questions about whether the act was, in fact, a breach of an obligation. The breach of obligations can take on many forms, thus the determination of it will depend on the nature of the act and the intention surrounding it. This requires the ascertainment of the rights and obligations of each party, as well as the nature of the act in question, at least the burden of proof. The last stage of enforcement is through remedies. This is the act of securing some form

of relief for a suffered loss or to prevent a perceived or real injustice. Measures will attempt to restore the position of the aggrieved party and act to punish or prevent the repetition of certain conduct.

2. Legal Framework for Commercial Contracts in Jordan

The general rule was that where the parties had failed to make a governing choice of law for their contract, the provision of the Jordanian Private International Law Act applied, and thus the proper law for the contract would be the law of the state with which it was most closely connected. The High Court decided that the Commercial Code must be treated as a whole, and the general principles must yield in the case of individual provisions which differed from the common law.³

In contrast to other aspects of commercial law, Jordan's framework for commercial contracts and transactions is robust, thus providing special rules for commercial contracts and giving special protection to merchants. The Jordanian legal framework for commercial contracts is a complex system which has evolved over many years. The laws relating to commercial contracts are found in a confusing myriad of statutes, regulations, and international conventions. Commercial transactions are primarily governed by the Civil Code as well as the Commercial Code and other relevant legislation. It was always open to a person conducting a commercial activity to opt out of the general law of contract and into the commercial law, and this was simply done by express agreement.⁴

2.1. Applicable laws and regulations

This being said, any foreign law chosen will only be directly used to determine the contract; it would not become the actual law of Jordan. In instances where there is a contract involving a foreign party, the foreign party's state may ratify an agreement with Jordan allowing its law to be enforced by the foreign party. Such cases may even result in Jordan enforcing judgements from the foreign state in order to uphold accountability for the contract. In conclusion, the provisions of the Civil Code are law in the broadest sense, as they are the backbone of all contracts in Jordan and are supplemented by various other sources.

While the Civil Code is the primary source of contract law in Jordan, it is imperative to note that it is not the exclusive source. Jordan is a mixed legal system which has continuing influences from Islamic law, customary law and tribal traditions. This is important due to the fact that Article 6 of the Civil Code allows parties to a contract to select the law they wish to govern it - even if it is a foreign law. If the law chosen is not Jordanian law, the parties must indirectly enforce their contract by using the provisions of the Civil Code itself. It is very common for parties to choose to use

Sharia law to govern their contracts; however this does not mean that Sharia becomes the direct source of law with regard to contracts in Jordan. Primarily, it means that the general precepts of Sharia regarding justice and public policy will be utilized in tandem with the relevant provisions of the Civil Code.⁵

In Jordan, the legal accountability for commercial contracts is situated within the framework of private law, and more specifically, the Law of Contracts. This area of law is primarily comprised of the comprehensive provisions outlined in the Civil Code. Established in 1976, the Jordanian Civil Code is modelled after its Egyptian counterpart and was a break from the prior civil law tradition in Jordan that was heavily influenced by the French legal system of the 19th Century. Because of its comprehensive nature, the Civil Code is the primary source of contract law and thus legal accountability for contracts in Jordan.

2.2. Key provisions related to legal accountability

The Law of Commerce in Jordan is slightly more comprehensive on the issue, however, with a more specific stance on certain types of contracts and the form of accountability derived from a default. Articles 32 through to 35 on commercial transactions and trade carry a provision for liability through damages or compensation in the event of non-performance, vice or delay in a contract. This stipulation is similar to the majority of the civil code's position, but relevance to specific performance, damages, and compensation give a clearer indication of the consequences and form of liability following a breach.⁶

2.3. Role of the court system in enforcing accountability

The judiciary is an important aspect of any legal system since it plays a central role in interpreting laws and regulations and providing decisions on disputes. The effectiveness of laws depends on the presence of an independent and efficient court system with judges who are well-versed in the subject matter. The Jordanian court system is an integrated system where civil, Sharia, and special courts operate concurrently. The judiciary is generally considered to be independent; however, the executive branch exerts influence in the appointment, promotion, and removal of judges. With regard to knowledgeable judges, there is a mixed perception. In the context of commercial disputes, the most effective court is considered to be the Amman Court of First Instance. This court has a panel of professional judges trained in business law and a set of procedures to ensure fast resolution of disputes. Appeals are made to the Court of Appeals and the Court of Cassation. Although no data was found on the success rate of appeals, it is likely that a new judgment is more in favor of the prevailing party in a higher court. A drawback in the Jordanian judiciary is the relative lack of certainty in law due to its common law and civil law

influences. This is a disincentive for foreign investors who are used to clear precedents in common law or comprehensible statutes in civil law. Nevertheless, the court system is still the primary means of enforcing legal accountability in commercial contracts.

3. Types of Legal Accountability in Commercial Contracts

In order to remedy the breach of contract, it is necessary for the type of liability incurred to be established. Liability for breach of contract is an obligation that arises by operation of law to make good on a loss suffered due to the breach of the contract. The law provides that a party is entitled to some form of right or benefit for which he has contracted, and this right is protected by the award of damages. In Jordan legislation, damages are divided into two distinct categories: general damages and special damages. General damages are those that the law presumes to be the natural result of the breach of contract, while special damages are losses that do not flow naturally from the breach but which the party in default had prior knowledge of. In addition to the award of damages for loss suffered by the innocent party, the law may also impose various forms of equitable remedies on the party in default, such as specific performance or an injunction.⁷

Breach of contract is a critical component of legal accountability in commercial contracts and occurs when one party fails to comply with the terms of the contract. There are various ways in which breach of contract can occur, and these are normally distinguished by the degree of severity in the non-performance. The most serious form of breach is termed 'repudiatory breach' and occurs when one party expressly or implicitly refuses to perform the contract. This allows the 'innocent' party to bring the contract to an end and claim damages for the losses suffered as a result. The second form of breach is a failure to perform the contract on the date agreed (delay). This allows the innocent party to claim damages for any losses incurred as a result of the delay, providing that the delay was not caused by an event which discharged the contract (see 3.3). The final form of breach is known as 'immaterial breach' and occurs when there has been incomplete performance of the contract.⁸

3.1. Breach of contract and remedies

The next remedy to be considered is damages. A claimant who is awarded damages is to be placed in the position they would have been in had the contract been properly performed. There are two types of damages that may be awarded: direct and consequential. Direct damages are those that flow naturally from the breach of contract, while consequential damages are those that arise from the special circumstances of the case and are awarded on the basis that the party in breach

knew or should have known about these circumstances and that it would result in more loss upon breach of contract. The measure of damages and any limitation on liability will depend greatly on the terms of the contract and the circumstances of the case.⁹

The first remedy the innocent party may seek is that of specific performance. This is an order by the court requiring the party in breach to carry out their obligations under the contract. An order for specific performance is a discretionary remedy and will not be granted if it is more prejudicial to the defendant than it is beneficial to the claimant. Specific performance is not commonly granted as damages are usually a sufficient remedy; it is generally only deemed appropriate in cases where the subject matter of the contract is unique.

In the event of breach of contract, the innocent party will want to know what their legal position is and what remedies are available to them. The party in breach will want to know what consequences they may face and to what extent they may be able to limit the damage caused. It is important to note here the well-established Jordanian legal principle that commercial agreements are to be honored and that the courts will take every possible step to enforce agreements. This principle is based on Sharia law, which underpins the Jordanian legal system, making it a matter of public policy that parties should be held to their agreements.¹⁰

3.2. Liability for misrepresentation or fraud

Liability for misrepresentation or fraud is founded upon a false statement or representation of fact by a party which induces the other party to contract with him. The statement can be in the form of words or conduct, as silence can amount to a representation. If it can be proved that the representation was false and was made fraudulently with the intention that it should be acted on, the representor is said to be fraudulent. If the representor did not have the belief on reasonable grounds that the statement was true, this is constructive fraud. If the false statement was made innocently, as in the representor did believe the statement was true, this is innocent misrepresentation.¹¹ It is important that the statement made was one of fact, as statements of opinion are not actionable unless the representor is of an expertise background on the subject of opinion and his ability to form an opinion was in doubt. If the statement was one of fact, it must also induce the contract.¹²

3.3. Consequences of non-performance or delay

The particular remedy of damages for non-performance or delay in contract is modified by the assessment of the loss to the creditor with reference to whether or not he has some interest in the maintenance of a contractual relationship with the defendant, or only an interest in the substance of the contract. If the interest is in the

contractual relationship, the defaulting defendant will be able to absolve himself from the contractual obligation by paying damages assessed by the loss of the contractual right. This is the principle in a line of cases where contracts for personal service have been discharged by damages measured according to the value of the services to the promisee.

The creditor of a non-performing contract may elect to treat the contract as discharged and bring an action for debt or damages. However, it is more likely that he will require performance at some future date. The consequence of discharge in this way always leads to damages being regarded as the primary remedy. The damages will be measured by the value to the creditor of the defendant's promised performance, but he must give credit for any expenses saved and for any gains avoided by not having to undertake performance. The general rule as to the measurement of damages for loss resulting from a breach of contract is that the injured party is to be placed, so far as money can do it, in the same position, as nearly as possible, as if the contract had been performed.

3.4. Dispute resolution mechanisms

Compared with the United Nations Convention on the Use of Electronic Communications in International Contracts (the UNCITRAL Model Law on Electronic Commerce), Jordan has not passed specific legislation related to online contracts. Article 13 of the UNCITRAL model law ensures the functional and technological neutrality of the law, stating that no signature should be denied legal effect, including that of forming a contract. Nonetheless, Jordan passed Electronic Transactions Law No. 85 in 2001. Article 8 of the ETA states that the offer and acceptance and revocation of an offer can be conducted electronically.¹³

4. Ensuring Legal Accountability in Commercial Contracts

Article 1 of the CISG provides that the Convention shall apply to contracts of the sale of goods between parties whose places of business are in different States when the States are Contracting States. Given its international focus, the CISG contains its own rules governing the conflicts of law at articles 95-97. These rules determine when the CISG will apply and when it will defer to domestic law. One problem is that rules on conflict of law differ between different countries, thus the CISG has created its own rules in order to establish a coherent and consistent method for establishing the applicability of the CISG.¹⁴In the event that the CISG does not cover a particular issue or the States have opted out of the Convention in favor of their domestic law, the CISG will still apply to contractual issues governed by the CISG. Litigants in States that apply the CISG will benefit from the CISG's efforts to unify legal positions surrounding international commercial contracts and should experience consistency

in judicial interpretation of CISG provisions as the courts will be required to take into consideration the international character of the Convention and the need to promote uniformity in its application (CISG Article 7).

4.1. Drafting effective contract terms and conditions

A possible solution to enhance the understanding of contract terms and conditions is to use visual aids such as flow charts or decision trees, especially for contracts of great complexity. Such a method was employed in a Turkish case where a complex international construction contract was evidenced by hundreds of pages of detailed terms and conditions. The seller made a flow chart to visually explain the obligations of the buyer, and used this chart to demonstrate the specific obligation that the buyer had failed to comply with. The court found this chart to effectively demonstrate the seller's claim, and as such held with the terms and conditions that the seller was entitled to injunctive relief.

Precision and clarity are key elements to effective terms and conditions, and goes much further than mere use of simple language as addressed in the Plain English section 2.2. A common mistake is attempt to use technical legal terms to give the document an 'official' feel, however such terminology may be misunderstood and misinterpreted by the receiving party.¹⁵ Where there exists any doubt to the meaning of wording in the terms and conditions, the usual principle is *contra proferentem*, where the ambiguous term will be interpreted against the party who put it forward. This leads to obvious potential detriment, and it is for this reason that it is essential for legal advisors to ensure that all terms and conditions are fully understood by the parties.

4.2. Importance of clear communication and documentation

Documentation is the linchpin of communication in modern business. Contracts are rarely made in simple straightforward terms and a handshake. Yet even agreements made in such an informal way have the potential to affect legal rights and duties. It was stated in *Exxonmobil Marine Ltd v Arab Republic of Egypt* that while parties may have reached an agreement, if there is no documented evidence of the terms of the agreement, the "purse" of the agreement "may just as easily slip" and not provide sufficient security. In the event of a dispute over an undocumented agreement, the law will imply terms in the agreement or construe the agreement as something different from its true object. These are speculative processes in which the court attempts to do what is fair given the circumstances but may have the effect of altering the actual intentions of the parties or frustrating the justifiable expectations of one or the other of them. In such instances, when the agreement concerns some significant rights or duties, the speculative process can produce a

result which is far removed from the true agreement, and a party may find that he is bound to something to which he was unwilling to consent.¹⁶ This will lead to an unsatisfactory bargain, and more likely than not, the unaware party will seek to ascertain his legal rights incompletely. Non-compliance with legal obligations cannot be a satisfactory remedy for any dispute. A party who knows and understands his obligations under an agreement is less likely to infringe those obligations, and this is the present view on the doctrine of rule and compliance. In short, the terms agreed must be translated into the rights and duties as prescribed by the agreement, and evidence of the agreement must be set out in a way that leaves no room for inconsistent speculative or assumed terms.

This need can only be sufficiently fulfilled when there is clear communication between the parties as to the terms and object of the contract.

"In everyday life, when people make promises to each other in the course of their conversations, they do so without any formality. But when their promises affect legal rights and obligations of economic significance, they do not always realize the need to express them in terms which are not open to different interpretations by the parties because under the stress of economic adversity, differing interpretations may lead to much unpleasantness and may result in litigation which is itself an additional economic loss."

4.3. Role of legal advisors and experts in ensuring accountability

Legal Professionalism Defined The service rendered by legal advisors can be made with reference to contracts and is simple to understand. A legal advisor is a representative to whom a client delegates authority to understand a legal situation, interpret the law and make it applicable to the client's specific circumstances, in order to achieve the desired result without creating unnecessary legal risk. The legal advisor guides and assists the client in creating legal relationships and in taking decisions which carry legal consequences. All of this must be done with a view to preventing the client from legal risk not within the client's parameters. The legal advisor must bear the onus of responsibility where he must understand that if the advice is wrong or if matter has been overlooked, the client will be worse off and legal advisors' negligence may render him liable. Failure to appreciate this is a departure from legal professionalism. Coming back to the topic, legal advisors are indeed the experts in the understanding and formation of legal relationships and it is submitted that they are in the best position to advise on ensuring accountability in commercial contracts and preventing legal risk. This can be highlighted with contrast to alternative modes of ensuring accountability.¹⁷

4.4. Compliance with local laws and regulations

The first thing to do is make sure that the law of the country has a strong connection with the contract. This connection is important because it identifies the country which has the most significant relationship with the transaction or, more plainly, the country most involved. This can be the country in which the contract says a certain act must be performed. An example is a Jordanian lease agreement whereby it is usual for the lease to specify that rent should be paid at the beginning of each month. If the lessee fails to pay rent at the start of the month, he has failed to perform his obligation and thus the agreement can be terminated by the lessor (see art 94 Lease law 20/2007). In this situation, this provision has a strong connection with the law of Jordan as it is an agreement for a lease in Jordan, and thus we would look to the law of Jordan to see whether such a provision can be enforced.

This step is probably the most important step. It ensures that a commercial contract is not only a valid document but also enforces rights and duties prescribed by it. Knowing what local law is and how it will affect the validity and enforceability of a certain provision in a contract is a complex issue, often requiring the assistance of legal experts. However, a basic understanding of what you need to know can save time and legal expense.¹⁹²⁰

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